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Development Strategy of the Widhya Asih Orphanages Program Through Voluntourism

Sidhi Bayu Turker¹, Kadek Widyastuti², Ni Made Erpia Ordani Astuti³

¹ Applied D4 Degree Program in Hospitality Management, Faculty of Vocational, Dhyana Pura University

² Applied Undergraduate Program D4 Hospitality Management, Faculty of Vocational, Dhyana Pura University

³ Family Education Studies Program, Faculty of Economics, Business and Humanities, Dhyana Pura University

Correspondence: Sidhi Bayu Turker. Jalan Tegaljaya, Dalung 80361, Kuta Utara, Badung, Bali, Indonesia
Email: sidhiturker@undhirabali.ac.id

Abstract

The Numbers of voluntourists from several developed countries shows promising growth before the pandemic Covid-19. Tourists who carry out voluntourism activities are increasing and this shows that voluntourism has an opportunity to be developed. Bali as a world tourist destination can take the opportunity to develop voluntourism as a promising product. The early observation indicated that one of the places that are interesting to be used as volunteer activities is the Orphanage. The Widhya Asih Orphanages foundation in Bali has 6 Orphanages that have potential opportunities to make voluntourism programs to support sustainable tourism development in Bali. This study focus on how far the perceptions and motivations of the Widhya Asih Orphanages managers see voluntourism as a strategy for developing the program in contributing and supporting sustainable tourism development in Bali. The method used in this research is a qualitative method through Data Collection Procedures which includes qualitative observations, qualitative interviews, and qualitative documents. Data collection was focused on the perceptions and motivations of the Widhya Asih Orphanages Managers, the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats faced by Widhya Asih Orphanages in adapting voluntourism activities. Through this research, it is hoped that Widhya Asih Orphanages can develop its program strategies more openly through voluntourism to attract tourists to choose Widhya Asih Orphanages as a place to carry out voluntourism activities. Besides that, this research also gave a model of organizing voluntourism for Orphanages in general.

Keywords: Perception, Motivation, Strategy, Voluntourism, Sustainability

1. Introduction

The world tourism industry before the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic at the end of 2019 showed a positive direction but has decreased since 2020. Based on data highlights from the UN-WTO (2021) the number of world tourists in 2019 increased by 4% (1.5 billion) compared to in 2018 which reached 1.4 billion. While in 2020 it decreased to 381 million, decreased by 74%. The decline was a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. This positive growth before 2020 is supported by the emergence of various new tourism products such as voluntourism. Interest in voluntourism tourists before the Covid-19 pandemic from several developed countries showed promising growth (Holmes, et al., 2009). Tourists who carry out voluntourism activities are increasing and this shows that

voluntourism has the opportunity to be developed. Bali as a world tourist destination can take the opportunity to develop voluntourism as a superior product. The results of the observation show that one of the places that are interested in volunteering is The Widhya Asih Orphanages that managed by Widhya Asih Foundation.

The Widhya Asih Foundation through their Orphanages has potential opportunities to support tourism development in Bali with voluntourism activities. So far, Widya Asih Orphanages programs or activities are still limited to routine learning and education activities, even though so far they have also received tourist visits who carry out social work activities but are not programmed and structured as they should be. To be able to capture better opportunities and develop in the use of voluntourism tourists, it is necessary to conduct research studies on voluntourism programs that can become an added value for the Widya Asih Orphanages so that it is beneficial for the development of the Widhya Asih Orphanages program, the community and industry players, tourism, and at the same time support the development of the quality of sustainable tourism development in Bali.

This research was conducted to determine the perception and motivation of Widhya Asih managers to see voluntourism as a strategy in contributing, and supporting sustainable tourism development in Bali. Based on this goal, it is hoped that the development of the Widya Asih Orphanages program can be an attraction for voluntourism tourists in supporting the quality of tourism development in Bali through social work activities at the Widhya Asih Orphanages. This study also provides a model and strategy for developing a voluntourism program at the Widya Asih Orphanages as an excellent alternative program in supporting the development of sustainable tourism in Bali. The answer to the formulation of the problem in this study is based on several theories, namely voluntourism, voluntourism principles, perception, motivation, consumer behavior, tourism demand and supply, sustainable tourism development.

2. Method

This research was conducted at 6 (six) Widhya Asih Orphanages spread across Melaya, Blimbingsari, Badung, Bangli, Singaraja, and Amlapura. The research method used is qualitative methods which is a form of research design through several stages of the process starting from collecting, analyzing, and integrating qualitative data in a study. Data collection techniques were carried out through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. In this study, the clarity and adequacy of the theory are combined or modified with the experience of the leaders of the Widhya Asih Orphanages, perceptions and motivations of the organizers of the Widhya Asih Orphanages, and approaches to other aspects such as motives, experiences, and impacts of the implementation of voluntourism that has been carried out. The approach taken is also intended to help understand the experiences of those who are being researched and can then be applied and used as a better management model.

The analyzed data is presented in two forms, namely an analysis of the perception and motivation of the Widhya Asih Orphanages organizers, and an analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats. The two forms are combined to produce a strategy for developing voluntourism products in the Widhya Asih Orphanages, and also a model for organizing voluntourism in the Widhya Asih Orphanages.

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the study included field observations, filling out questionnaires, and supported by in-depth interviews with the leaders of the Widhya Asih Orphanages. The main respondents and informants are the Chairperson while the supporting informants are members of the community and foreign student tourists from Dhyana Pura University who have carried out voluntourism activities at the Widhya Asih Orphanages. Observations were made in all 6 Widhya Asih Orphanages while filling out the questionnaire and more in-depth interviews were conducted in four Orphanages. Observations have been made since early 2020 shortly after the Covid-19 pandemic, while questionnaires and in-depth interviews were conducted at Orphanages in Melaya, Blimbingsari, Badung, and Bangli due to the implementation of the Health protocol. The results of further research are described as follows.

3.1 Profile of the Widhya Asih Orphanages

3.1.1 History of Establishment

Seeing a large number of school-age children in several places in Bali who have not been able to receive a proper education, the leaders of the Protestant Christian Church in Bali (GKPB), took the initiative to establish a dormitory to accommodate and help poor and neglected children so that they can get a proper education. The hostel was first established in 1975 under the name Widhya Pura Asrama. Then on its way, it grew to 6 which are located in 6 districts in Bali. At first, this dormitory was shaded by the Widhya Pura Foundation which was in charge of Widhya Pura Education and Widhya Pura Dormitory. In 1990, the Widhya Pura Dormitory Division (Orphanage) separated itself from the Widhya Pura Foundation by forming a new Foundation with the name "Widhya Asih Orphanages" at Notary K. Rames Iswara, SH, with Deed Number 117, dated January 25, 1990, and since being registered with the Bali Provincial Department of Social Affairs, since then all Widhya Pura dormitory units have been changed to the Widhya Asih Orphanages and are under the auspices of the "Widhya Asih Orphanage" Foundation. Foster children are children who come from economically disadvantaged families, orphans, and neglected.

3.1.2 Vision and Mission

Vision: To become a social institution that works to help reduce poverty in people in Bali.

Mission: Helping underprivileged children to be able to help themselves break the wheel of poverty by providing: 1. Care and protection of children in Widhya Asih Orphanages and family- based; 2. Providing nutritious food and Physical and Spiritual Health; 3. Formal education; 4. Life skills training; 5. Provide a comfortable, safe, and clean place to live.

3.1.3 Number of Fostered Children

Table 3.1: The total number of Foster Children, Employer, and Volontourists Widhya Asih Orphanages 2021

WIDHYA ASIH ORPHANAGES BALI								
DATA: Number of Childrens, Employer, Volontourists								
No.	Name of Orphanages	No of Childrens	Boys	Girls	Number Employer	Number Volontourist (3)	Number Days (4)	Average Days (5)
1	Blimbingsari	75	42	33	10	131	641	4.9
2	Singaraja	94	39	55	9	86	577	6.7
3	Badung	40	18	22	5	84	491	5.8
4	Melaya	77	31	46	10	200	442	2.2
5	Bangli	30	16	14	3	2	10	5.0
6	Amlapura	22	11	11	3	24	259	10.8
	TOTAL	338	157	181	40	527	2,420	4.59

Based on the data above, the total number of foster children (1) is 338 consisting of 157 male foster children and 181 female foster children. This comparison of numbers is a note for both organizers, and volontourists that the

activities carried out in the orphanage and outside the orphanage are paid attention to the form of activities that are followed by the composition of the interests of men and women.

The number of volunteers who carried out voluntourism activities (3,4,5) in 2019 (before the Covid 19 Pandemic) the total number was 527 people who carried out voluntourism activities in a total of 2,420 days or an average per year person per day is 4.59 days. From these data, the average interest of voluntourists in voluntourism activities is quite promising to be considered by orphanage managers in designing more focused voluntourism activities.

Based on the location of the orphanage, the highest interest in volunteering for volunteer activities (3) chose Melaya (West Bali) of 200 people, followed by Blimbingsari of 131 people, Singaraja (North of Bali) 86 people, Badung (South of Bali) 84 people, Amlapura (East of Bali) 24 people, and Bangli (Middle of Bali) 2 people. This composition can help the manager of each orphanage to design volunteer activities that can attract more volunteers to visit. The caretaker of an orphanage with a small number of voluntourists can study observation at an orphanage that receives more voluntourist visits. The countries of origin for the volunteers are Australia, Japan, Singapore, Germany, China, and Indonesia itself. From the results of interviews, volunteers from Japan dominated the visit, followed by tourists from Germany, Australia, Singapore, and China. Orphanage managers can start collaborating with educational institutions to increase knowledge about cross-cultural understanding by studying the cultural characteristics of tourists from these countries so that they can open their horizons in accepting voluntourism activities.

3.1.4 Observations of voluntourism activities at Widhya Asih Orphanages

All Heads of Widhya Asih Orphanages have held voluntourism activities in their respective for both foreign tourists and domestic tourists which are coordinated and recommended by the Head of the Widhya Asih Foundation, and also the volunteer sending agency recommended by the Head of the Widhya Asih Foundation. The period time for the implementation of voluntourism varies from less than a week to several weeks. Some of them are carried out periodically every year. But since the Covid-19 pandemic, voluntourism activities at all Orphanages have not been allowed.

The Heads of Widhya Asih Orphanages have not made the voluntourism program a routine and planned program even though they know that voluntourism activities provide benefits to Orphanages and the surrounding community based on experience in previous implementations. Widhya Asih Orphanages does not yet have a flow model for organizing voluntourism activities so the activities carried out so far are not structured so that they do not guarantee a sense of security and comfort in organizing voluntourism activities. Volunteer age restrictions have not been implemented and all voluntourists are accepted without going through proper screening.

3.2 Perceptions of Widhya Asih Orphanages Leaders

The perception of the leadership of Widhya Asih Orphanages about efforts to make voluntourism a potential routine program to support the development of the tourism industry in Bali shows a positive thing. The results of the study show that volunteerism has a great opportunity to be a potential choice that can enrich the form and type of the Widhya Asih Orphanages program because so far voluntourism activities are highly favored by volunteers and the children of Widhya Asih Orphanages students because the benefits obtained can be felt directly both institutionally and directly. Personally by Widhya Asih Orphanages leaders and students. For them, it is a matter of pride that voluntourism activities can play a positive role in supporting the quality of sustainable tourism development in Bali. Widhya Asih Orphanages need volunteers to provide experience and reinforcement for students and also for tourists.

The Widhya Asih Orphanages results of the study show that the managers of Widhya Asih Orphanages understand the voluntourist views on the implementation of voluntourism activities at Widhya Asih Orphanages on their previous experiences. For the manager of Widhya Asih Orphanages, voluntourism activities are closely related to individual beliefs about all the risks associated with the experience, especially feelings or emotional components (eg, uncertainty, worry, anxiety) and the possibility of failure of plans that have been planned (Pieniak et al., 2008).

The perception of Widhya Asih Orphanages manager emphasizes the importance of organizing voluntourism that can fulfill voluntourist satisfaction in the form of security and comfort in carrying out voluntourism activities. The perception of Widhya Asih Orphanages organizer Widhya Asih Orphanages also shows that the approach taken by volunteering requires a special approach, especially communication that must be carried out before the volunteer activity is carried out.

Activities carried out by voluntourists are carried out through a cognitive-normative approach as stated by Plog (1972) in Pitana (Pitana, et al., 2009, 48), so all voluntourism activities can be (1) Allocentric, namely tourists who want to visit places that unknown, adventurous, and utilize the facilities provided by the local community; (2) Psychocentric, namely tourists who only want to visit tourist destinations that already have facilities with the same standards as those in their own country. They travel with a definite program and take advantage of facilities with international standards; (3) Mid-centric, located between allocentric, and psychometric. Thus it can be said that Volunteer Tourism is a travel activity associated with various social work activities in various forms (such as culture, education, environment, etc.) together and with a group of people who are left behind in a tourist destination and its surroundings without expecting anything in return. On the contrary, provide some of the funds that come from himself or on his initiative to dig up funds to finance his social work activities based on the principles of sustainable tourism development.

From the description above, the organizers of Widhya Asih Orphanages understand that the implementation of voluntourism is not only centered on the safety and comfort of the implementation of voluntourism but is also influenced by the forms and types of activities that can fulfill tourist satisfaction in the planning and selection process of voluntourism activities carried out with the community by considering various integrated approaches. Which not only satisfies tourists but also provides clear benefits to the receiving community.

3.3 Motivation of Widhya Asih Orphanages Leaders

The Motivation of Widhya Asih Orphanages Leaders has a strong motivation to accept and organize voluntourism activities carried out in the Widhya Asih Orphanages Leaders environment because directly and indirectly, these activities provide benefits for students to gain experience interacting with tourists which strengthens their enthusiasm and desire to excel. For institutions, the benefits in the form of programs, funds, and tourist support make Widhya Asih Orphanages leaders motivated to make volunteerism a positive value and can raise the quality of services and take part in contributing to improving the quality of tourism development in Bali. Their motivation is supported by pride that Widhya Asih Orphanages can be a way for voluntourists to carry out social activities and gain experience not only for vacations but also new experiences by taking part in doing social activities with the community at Widhya Asih Orphanages. The relationship that exists between tourists and Widhya Asih Orphanages students is based on the authenticity approach of the relationship that exists not only when the activity is carried out but also continues with tourists and follow-up activities. The constructive relationship that exists between tourists and Widhya Asih Orphanages is one of the reinforcements that voluntourism can be an option favored by tourists. The results of the interview also show that tourists want inter-personal and intra-personal relationships that are built based on an existence that can strengthen each other so that tourists and Widhya Asih Orphanages get benefits and new experiences that can change their understanding of quality tourism. Voluntourism can be an alternative when voluntourism activities are aimed at strengthening and improving the quality of Widhya Asih Orphanages program activities.

For the organizers of Widhya Asih Orphanages, motivation is very important because motivation affects the level of responsibility for the successful implementation of volunteer activities, especially the importance of maintaining communication with volunteers for the continuation of similar programs in the future. This result is also in line with the opinion of Sidhi Turker (2021) who said motivation has an important role in planning a voluntourism activity because it is related to fulfilling the wishes of tourists to carry out successful and efficient voluntourism activities. The right motivation will be able to produce maximum results in an organization of voluntourism activities. In volunteer tourism activities, tourists are given motivation that can provide confidence that their wishes will be maximally accounted for, and therefore management is needed that can plan, organize and carry out these

voluntourism activities. Every activity carried out by voluntourists cannot be separated from the impetus and attitude to carry out activities in meeting the tourists' self-actualization needs.

The need for self-actualization is a person's full potential and personal ambition. Self-actualization needs can be in the form of creativity, spontaneity, and also problem-solving abilities. McClelland classifies human needs into three types, namely achievement, affiliation, and power. Need for achievement or the need for achievement is a need where humans want to achieve or show their competence to others. The need for achievement encourages a person to do things better to be recognized by others and by himself. While affiliation is the need for love, belonging, and social acceptance. The need for affiliation makes a person motivated to perform a behavior to be recognized by his social environment. In terms of power or the need for power or the need for power is the desire of someone to get power and have a higher authority than others.

Meanwhile, Maslow (in Samantha Lee, 2017) ranks human needs starting from the bottom to the top, namely (a) Physiological needs. This need is a basic need that concerns human survival such as oxygen, food, sleep, clean water, homeostatic abilities, and secretions; (b) Security requirements. This need is the fulfillment of a sense of human security in various forms including personal security, security in the financial sector, welfare, work, family security; (c) Social needs. As humans, social needs are manifested in interactions between humans in the form of friendship, the need to be loved, good family relationships, to relationships with colleagues; (d) The need for appreciation. This need is the fulfillment of the appreciation received by a person in the form of self-confidence, respect for others, respect and respect, and also a feeling of being recognized for having talents and abilities.

Based on the previous experience of organizing voluntourism, Widhya Asih Orphanages managers have a very positive and good motivation to do their best for voluntourism activities in Widhya Asih Orphanages environment because they understand the positive impact and benefits of voluntourism activities can be felt for the foster children and the continuation of the program. Widhya Asih Orphanages program in the future, moreover, voluntourism activities also provide quality for sustainable tourism activities in Bali.

3.4 Application of Voluntourism in Widhya Asih Orphanages

As a non-profit activity, voluntourism activities at Widhya Asih Orphanages need to be planned through a process specifically designed for the Widhya Asih Orphanages environment. In realizing the desire of volunteers to carry out their activities in Widhya Asih Orphanages support from various parties is needed, especially organizations sending and receiving volunteers. This is in line with the statement by Wearing (2001) which says that the approach and special handling of voluntourism activities are carried out by those who have experience and high social skills with receiving communities where voluntourism activities are a combination of travel and voluntary work activities with the community. Recipient organizations need to provide the energy, energy, and enthusiasm needed to realize the goals of voluntourism including offering the community involvement that is needed to fulfill their mission effectively. Therefore, sending and receiving organizations need cooperation to bring in voluntourism tourists. Sidhi Turker (2021) emphasized that this collaboration requires two approaches, namely (1) the voluntourism market, and (2) strategies to increase, manage, and retain volunteers. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a deeper exploration of the issues related to volunteers and explain the new paradigm needed to balance the supply and demand for volunteerism.

The results of interviews with tourists as stated by Sidhi Turker (2021) show that the interest of volunteers to serve in Orphanages is quite high. This opportunity is a challenge for Widhya Asih Orphanages managers to observe and approach the voluntourism market, especially concerning the supply and demand of voluntourism tourists. Widhya Asih Orphanages managers need to know in advance the needs of volunteers on the one hand and the other hand the needs of the community around Widhya Asih Orphanages. To understand this, it can be done by understanding the needs of voluntourists and the community based on several theoretical foundations such as voluntourism, voluntourism principles, consumption behavior, sustainable tourism development. These theories become the rationale for explaining the concept of research to see how tourists, tourism industry stakeholders, and voluntary tourist receiving institutions in Widhya Asih Orphanages implement their activities by principles of sustainable tourism development.

Concerning to the theory of voluntourism and the principles of voluntourism, voluntourism activities in Widhya Asih Orphanages require a separate approach because the Widhya Asih Orphanages' vision and mission have specific understandings and objectives that are different from the case if carried out in the community or tourist village. However, the principles of implementation have similarities, including the characteristics or characteristics of the activities displayed by Widhya Asih Orphanages. Sarah (2010) suggests that there must be at least 8 (eight) things that must be done and require deep attention that underlies Volunteer Tourism activities so that they have their characteristics, namely Service, Experience, Investment, Repetition, Passion, Purpose, Authenticity, and Learning.

The eight principles are (1) Service is the heart between voluntourism and tourism without service, success will not be achieved and satisfactory; (2). The Experience here refers to two aspects, namely experiences that are obtained personally (what occurs) and experiences in thinking patterns (wisdom, personal insight, and others). Each of these aspects is interrelated with each other and influences each other between volunteering and touristic activities; (3) Investment is a product that can be measured financially and is valid over time and investment is very important in the context of voluntourism and tourism industry. Although money is important, time is also an important commodity that supports the future sustainability of Volunteer Tourism as a new industry; (4) Repetition is the life and death of voluntourism. Volunteers need to maintain existing relationships and return to continue their mission and activities. For volunteers, this condition is a kind of dogma that they must return to that place; (5) Passion is a form of readiness for patience inside and out and requires its sacrifices which have to be prepared from the start by volunteers because without this patience, everything feels flat, aimless, and utterly disappointing, not only for the person concerned but for all the people involved in the process. the Volunteer Tourism activities; (6) Purpose colors the direction of a person's goals for participating in Volunteer Tourism activities. The purpose here is to give meaning and color and at the same time answer why someone does Volunteer Tourism activities; (7) Authenticity is a challenge for the volunteers how they can keep everything running according to the choices and plans so that the continuity of the activity can take place continuously; (8) Learning is a continuous learning process and the experiences gained by volunteers are part of self-forging and contribute to personal development as part of life-long learning that takes place continuously.

Furthermore, the use of perception and motivation theory is used to see the extent to which Widhya Asih Orphanages organizers can see voluntourism opportunities as an activity that can support the presence of Widhya Asih Orphanages as an institution that can adopt the interests and needs of volunteers to carry out holiday activities and social work at Widhya Asih Orphanages and how it can fulfill their wishes and needs. volunteer satisfaction. Positive perceptions and motivations become the basic strength for Widhya Asih Orphanages organizers in planning voluntourism activities so that they are successful and efficient under the character and needs of the Widhya Asih Orphanages itself. Wearing (2001) says that the form of Voluntourism activities must be imbued with character building based on history, nature, and tradition for the needs of the community itself. The opinion above implies that tourism is not just a collection of commercial activities; it is also the ideological framing of history, nature, and tradition; a framing that has the power to reshape culture and nature according to its own needs. Although basically, voluntourism is non-profit, the activity should also provide economic benefits, therefore administrators need to understand as well as possible how the process of voluntourism demand and supply, as well as voluntourism tourist behavior, is outlined in offering forms of voluntourism activities and voluntourism tourists for institutions such as Widhya Asih Orphanages. The ability to understand and explore the workings of voluntourism is a principal thing to know. Sidhi Turker (2021) asserts that the voluntourism market is wide open for tourists from developed countries because voluntourism activities for tourists are a source of pride and personal satisfaction that is taught in their daily family life. Therefore, the interests and expectations of voluntourists need to be matched with voluntourism activities that can answer their needs. Stein (2009) sees the proportion of voluntourism activities as having a variety of forms according to the interests of the tourists themselves. Some tourists carry out these activities with the support of their funds or receive assistance from certain organizations that are designated with the terms and conditions set by donor agencies. The use of the theory of supply and demand for tourists and tourist behavior is used to ensure that voluntourism activities are directed towards the results and benefits received by tourists and Widhya Asih Orphanages as a unit.

3.5 *Voluntourism Implementation Strategy at Widhya Asih Orphanages*

The results of the study show that Widhya Asih Orphanages has strengths, weaknesses, challenges, and at the same time opportunities to make voluntourism activities a new force in improving the quality of the Widhya Asih Orphanages program with foster children and also in socializing with tourists who can provide new understanding for managers and children. foster Widhya Asih Orphanages about the impact and benefits of voluntourism activities. The following describes the results of the study as follows:

3.5.1 Strengths of Widhya Asih Orphanages as a venue for voluntourism

- Widhya Asih Orphanages has experience doing voluntourism activities
- Widhya Asih Orphanages has a variety of program offerings that can be carried out by volunteers, for example providing cooking training, making snacks, language courses, and so on that can be collaborated with or with the community.
- Widhya Asih Orphanages can be reached easily
- Widhya Asih Orphanages has collaborations with educational institutions which can be included in various voluntary cooperation activities
- Widhya Asih Orphanages as part of the church institution has a partner in cooperation with various institutions abroad, especially developed countries that send a lot of voluntourism tourists.

3.5.2 Weaknesses of Widhya Asih Orphanages as venues for voluntourism

- Widhya Asih Orphanages does not yet have a model format for organizing voluntourism activities
- Widhya Asih Orphanages personnel are limited so they do not have special supervisors
- Widhya Asih Orphanages has limited funds in full support of voluntourism activities
- Widhya Asih Orphanages cannot provide many activities because of the limited number of students and the age limit cannot do all types of voluntourism activities
- Limitations of direct communication due to limited internet services.

3.5.3 Opportunities for Widhya Asih Orphanages to make volunteerism a flagship program

- Voluntourism can raise the quality of Widhya Asih Orphanages services to increase public trust
- The cooperation that is owned by both educational institutions, other institutions, and partners from abroad through the parent organization makes it very possible for this voluntourism program to be carried out by Widhya Asih Orphanages.
- Bali as a leading tourist destination has its charm. Moreover, research results (Sidhi Turker, 2021) show that interest in volunteering in Orphanages is quite positive.
- Widhya Asih Orphanages can combine voluntourism activities by spending time visiting tourist attractions around Widhya Asih Orphanages and can also introduce nearby tourist villages by combining various kinds of cultural activities.

3.5.4 Widhya Asih Orphanages challenges in developing volunteerism as a flagship program

- The main challenge is the weather because the implementation of voluntourism activities during the rainy season cannot be predicted.
- Voluntourism activities need to be handled carefully to minimize negative impacts that may occur, for example in predators, sex abuse, and other negative things.
- To carry out multi-voluntourism activities, Widhya Asih Orphanages managers need to increase cooperation with tourist villages, or stakeholders to increase mutually beneficial cooperation.

Based on the results of a study on the strengths, weaknesses, threats, and challenges faced by Widhya Asih Orphanages also the results of a study on perceptions, motivations of Widhya Asih Orphanages, some strategies can be applied. The voluntourism program in this new era has attracted the attention of stakeholders to pay attention to the holistic approach to Safety, Health, Hygiene, Brand, Value, and Capacity Management. In interviews with the managers of Widhya Asih Orphanages, the form and type of outdoor voluntourism activities require new strengthening of Standard Operating Procedures for Safety and Hygiene without reducing the meaning

of social relations with the community. Sidhi Turker (2022) mentions that all of these approaches require time, process, and cooperation from tourism stakeholders. For organizers, what is currently being carried out in the community is to socialize the CHSE Protocol (Cleanliness, Health, Safety, Environmental) from Indonesia Care through outreach and publications, training, simulations, and trials of volunteerism programs. The organizers of voluntourism are very aware that they are facing new opportunities and challenges in choosing a voluntourism program in the community based on the CHSE protocol while still paying attention to the principles of sustainable and quality tourism development.

Therefore, the organizers of voluntourism must be able to become a mediator between tourists and the community along with other stakeholders to build a form of sustainable cooperation. Yuwono (2020) stated that Indonesia is a potential place for the development of voluntourism because of the many activities that can be offered, especially environmental programs such as forestry programs, flora and fauna conservation activities. In line with that, The International Ecotourism Society supports voluntourism activities associated with ecotourism activities by issuing the Voluntourism Guidelines Project which emphasizes Uniting Conservation, Communities, and Sustainable Travel. They also emphasized that voluntourism activities are “responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well-being of local people.” For Indonesia, which is in the Pacific “ring of fire” circle, natural disasters often occur which require the support of volunteers to help deal with the recovery process due to various disasters. This opportunity also provides an opportunity for volunteers to carry out social work activities and at the same time travel. One form of strategy that can strengthen the presence of voluntourism in the development of sustainable tourism in Bali is to apply the model of organizing voluntourism as shown in Figures 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 below.

3.6 Model of organizing voluntourism in Widhya Asih Orphanages

Figure 3.1: Flow Model for Voluntourism Activity Venue Selection In Widhya Asih Orphanages

From Figure 3.1 above, it can be explained that the model for organizing voluntourism at Widhya Asih Orphanages is as follows:

1. Widhya Asih Orphanages is legally under the responsibility of the Widhya Asih Foundation so all forms of cooperation and activities that come from outside parties are required to be approved by the Widhya Asih Foundation because it is responsible for all internal and external activities of Widhya Asih Orphanages. That's why there are volunteers who come from individuals and institutions through the Widhya Asih Foundation.
2. The Widhya Asih Foundation will delegate the voluntourism activities according to the request of the voluntourist or sending agency which will then follow up on the voluntourism activities according to the plan.
3. In its implementation, Widhya Asih Orphanages can collaborate with educational institutions, communities, and other community organizations.

If we compare the model above with the Voluntourism Chain model published by the APEC Tourism Working Group (Milne, et al., 2018) as illustrated in the image below, the Voluntourism Implementation Model at the Orphanage has differences in the acceptance process because the Orphanage is under a Foundation which is legally responsible for all activities inside and outside the orphanage.

Figure 3.2: Voluntourism Chain APEC Tourism Working Group, 2018

Sources: *Voluntourism Best Practices: Promoting Inclusive Community-Based Sustainable Tourism Initiatives, Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) Tourism Working Group.*

The Voluntourism Chain model from the APEC Tourism Working Group can be a material for discussion between the Orphanage managers and the Protective Foundation and other stakeholders in producing a flow that is under the needs and needs of the institution and in this case according to the needs of the orphanage. Meanwhile, Sidhi Turker (2022) describes the Voluntourist Acceptance Model in the context of the tourism industry, especially in supporting sustainable tourism development as shown in Figure 3.3 below.

Figure 3.3: Flow Model for Voluntourism Activity Venue Selection

The diagram above illustrates the flow of voluntourist acceptance in tourist villages. VT tourists have the freedom to choose where to carry out voluntourism activities. They can choose the implementation site directly (in this case a tourist village), or through the sending institution which will forward it to the receiving institution. Recipient institutions will contact tourist villages that are of interest to tourists for vacations and voluntourism activities. This model is very open in nature and cannot be applied in Orphanages. However, orphanage managers need to study the model as shown in Figure 3.3 above to get a broader understanding.

4. Conclusions and Suggestions

4.1 Conclusion

Based on the discussion of the research results and discussion, it can be conveyed the conclusions of the research results regarding the development strategy of the Widhya Asih Orphanages Program as follows:

1. The perception of the organizers of the Widhya Asih Orphanages towards the implementation of voluntourism in Bali shows a positive thing and provides benefits for Orphanages in general. Voluntourism activities with orphanage children and the community are not only centered on the safety and comfort of the implementation of voluntourism but are also influenced by the forms and types of activities that can fulfill the satisfaction of tourists doing something through voluntourism activities with foster children.
2. The motivation of tourists in making volunteerism an interesting activity at the Widhya Asih orphanage shows high and positive interest because they can combine vacation activities and social work activities.
3. Voluntourism activities at the Widhya Asih Orphanage provide real and positive benefits. The experiences of tourists and voluntourism organizers show that voluntourism activities have a positive value not only for voluntourists but also for foster children and the surrounding community. Multi-effect benefits are obtained not only in the form of activity but various benefits in the economic, social, cultural fields, cultural exchange experiences, and communication.
4. Voluntourism can be used as a new strategy for the manager of the Widhya Asih Orphanage in supporting the sustainable development of Bali's tourism industry. This strategy is further strengthened by the findings of a model for organizing voluntourism in the Widhya Asih Orphanages environment which can be used as a reference and further developed by stakeholders, especially the organizers of voluntourism activities.

4.2 Suggestions

Based on the results of the study, suggestions can be submitted that can complement the implementation and implementation of voluntourism activities by the manager of Widhya Asih Orphanages as follows:

- a. Voluntourism to be developed continuously with the manager of Widhya Asih Orphanages through collaboration with the surrounding community, educational institutions, and other related parties whose implementation is based on the principles of community-based tourism and sustainable tourism development through a holistic approach with related parties so that the goals and focus of the benefits of volunteerism are successful and efficient.
- b. The application of health protocols. The CHSE (cleanliness, Health, Safety, Environmental) guidelines from Indonesia Care are recommended to be socialized and implemented as a necessity for new forms of tourism, especially by voluntourism organizers by implementing strict health protocols to provide a sense of trust, safety, comfort for tourists to carry out activities volunteerism in Bali.

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